

ANALYSIS OF THE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN

Murodkhonov Mukhammad Sodiq

Student of Kokaldosh secondary special school under
the Muslim Board of the Republic of Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6740001>

Annotation: Management as an area of science is an interdisciplinary network in which the achievements in economics, sociology, psychology, law, engineering and other disciplines, as well as the experience of the art of management are reflected. Modern management in Uzbekistan is a complex innovation science, which creates a favorable environment for the formation of a market economy, the development of entrepreneurship, the creation of certain conditions and competitiveness, the revival of physical and legal forms of economic freedom and responsibility. Is born at the same time. This article discusses the analysis of the management system in Uzbekistan.

Keywords: Uzbekistan, management, analysis, system, economy, market, innovation.

The subject of management is the study of the laws, principles and relationships of management at all levels of management. Management relations are an integral part of socio-economic relations and occur in various economic, organizational, social, labor, psychological and other forms. Management relationships represent a complex set of connections and interactions between employees under management, which means that management is primarily about managing people. In the management of the economy, the object of direct management consists of labor collectives and individual employees. Only through their labor activity are the material elements of production, that is, the tools and objects of labor, affected. The most basic cognitive style of management is the dialectical style, which helps management to uncover the essence of the social phenomena being studied.

The following other methods of management are also characteristic: a clear historical approach to the study of real events; a structural approach, structural analysis, economic experience, etc. that allows simultaneous analysis of all elements of the economic mechanism and the development of complete management decisions. The skill of management is to master all his methods, to be able to apply them correctly, to find the most effective in each specific situation. The continuous process of all management is management. This is the labor process of the management apparatus. In general, management can be described as follows: in terms of technology, organization and content. From the economic point of view, management is, first of all, a system of managing all

economic problems, managing people. From the social point of view of management - it is, first of all, meeting the social needs of labor communities, educating the person. The technology of the management process is the practical work performed by the management staff.

Thus, the management process is the coordinated action of the head of the administration and the people in order to achieve the set goal. At the problem stage, the main contradictions of the current state of the system are identified, what needs to be done to improve the performance of the system. The solution phase is the leader's transition to practical work. As soon as a decision is made, there is a clear impact on the managed systems, with separate simple management actions being taken. The methods of the management process are: information-analytical and organizational work. Information-analytical work includes: data collection, analysis, processing and transmission of information, development of options for management decisions, storage of information on options for management decisions, etc. Organizational work includes: explaining, persuading, motivating, assigning tasks, monitoring performance, influencing, and more.

Governing bodies and executors define the function of responsible management. These responsibilities are reflected in the Functional Division Regulations and Guidelines for Managers. Functional analysis of the management process forms the basis of the workload for each function, determines the number of managers, and designs the management system. If the controlled object has specific properties, the control functions also function. However, the following functions can be distinguished in the image of the enterprise:

1. management of the main production;
2. management of ancillary production;
3. product quality management;
4. labor and wage management, etc.

Each specific function is an integral part of the management function, which in turn is further subdivided into several parts. For example, basic production management, marketing, planning, incentives, and more. All functions are interconnected

In short, managing people requires not only making decisions, but also monitoring its implementation. Unfortunately, in many cases, the implementation of the management process in our lives is not fully organized, its organizational, content, technical aspects are not interconnected. The content of the management process is reflected in its functions. A management function is

a set of different tasks aimed at solving certain management problems. Governing bodies and executors define the function of responsible management.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Ibragimov R.G. Marketing. Tashkent, Sharq-Matbaa Joint Stock Company, 2002.
2. Samatov G'.A., Rustamova I.B., Sheripbayeva U.A. Agricultural Economics and Management.- T .: 2012. - 346 p.
3. Umrzoqov O'P., Toshboyev A.J., Rashidov J., Toshboyev A.A. Agricultural Economics and Management: A Textbook. - T .: Iqtisod - moliya, 2008. - 268 p.
4. Qosimova D.S. Management Theory: A Textbook. - T .: TDIU, 2009. - 208 p.